

Tween 20 and malachite green : a new reagent system for the micro-determination of phosphate in water and wastewater[†]

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A new reagent system is proposed for the micro-determination of phosphate in water and wastewater. The method is based on the reaction between ammonium molybdate, Tween 20 and malachite green which exhibit at $\lambda_{\max} = 600$ nm. Beer's law is obeyed upto 10 mg P/L. The use of malachite green is specially favoured because of its high sensitivity and the absence of interferences by silicates, an aspect that has hindered the use of the existing colorimetric methods. This method makes feasible measurements down to 0.01 mg P/L.

Several methods exist in the literature¹⁻⁴ for the detection and determination of phosphate in water. Among those, the colorimetric method predominates because of its simplicity, sensitivity and swiftness of obtaining results^{5,6}. In ordinary practice the analytical method¹ employed is the blue colorimetric phosphomolybdate method using stannous chloride as reducing agent. This method is very sensitive but is unfortunately subject to interferences especially from organic acids and ferric iron. It therefore became clear that for the purpose of the study a more accurate method of analysis has to be investigated. Therefore, for this purpose, literature is indicative³⁻⁸ that among the new techniques, based on the reaction of basic dyes in acid media, the use of malachite green is specially favoured because of its great sensitivity and the absence of interferences by silicate, an aspect that has hindered the use of molybdenum method⁵⁻⁸. In the present communication, a new reagent system is proposed which is based on the reaction between ammonium molybdate, Tween 20 and malachite green. The influence of various experimental conditions such as amount of reagent, kinetics of chromophore formation, Youden's^{9,10} blank determinations, effect of diverse species and stability of the reagent have been investigated.

Results and discussion

Absorption spectra :

The absorption spectra of the blank, standard and a water sample, showed the maximum at 600 nm, close to 610 nm reported by Veldhoven³ who used poly vinyl alcohol (PVA) instead of Tween 20. The peak at 600 nm is very distinct

and the absorbance at this wavelength is linearly correlated with concentration of the phosphate and is consistent with Beer's law. Beer's law is found to obey upto 10 mg/L. Hence, this wavelength was recommended for the determination of phosphate in water and wastewater samples. The blank value was found to be as 1.89 mg P₂O₅/L.

Kinetics of chromophore formation :

In order to find the time required for obtaining maximum stable absorbance, an experiment was carried out. A stable reading was obtained after 15 min, however, it is recommended to wait for 25 min before recording the maximum absorbance. The quantity of stabilizing agent (Tween 20) necessary in the final volume of reagent was studied. Above 2.9 mg, there is no appreciable increase in absorbance.

Possible error sources related to method accuracy :

After having established reaction conditions; i.e. the minimum quantities of reagent necessary to obtain the highest sensitivity in the present method, some aspects which influence the accuracy of results were studied for which the following aspects were taken into considerations; (i) what blank to use, and (ii) what type of calibration curve is most appropriate.

Regarding the first aspect, to know if the mixture of reagents plus water is the best reference, Youden's blank^{9,10}, or the relative absorbance versus amount of sample, was calculated. The intercept of the water straight line is to all intents and purposes at the origin while that for wastewater has a value of ~0.40, slightly less than the confidence limit

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for this intercept. This indicates that zero is the probable value and therefore straight line passes through the origin of the coordinates. These results reveals that the method blank is suitable as a reference for reading the samples because no constant sources of error due to matrix-analyte interaction was found.

Recovery determination :

In order to analyse the possible combined effects of matrix-analyte interaction the classical test of recovery was made using KH_2PO_4 , added to water and wastewater. The slopes of the standard addition curve for both water and wastewater samples as well as the calibration curve were calculated^{9,10}.

The results of the tests are in Table 1 and show that this method can be employed using a calibration curve prepared with a standard solution; it is not necessary to establish an additional standard curve, because of the good recovery in both cases. Statistical parameters obtained with the data from calibration curves for the proposed method are found as, slope (0.09), intercept (0.0387), correlation coefficient (0.9961), standard deviation (0.319), slope standard deviation (0.0032) and intercept deviation (0.0292).

Table 1. Comparison between the slopes of the calibration and the standard addition lines in water and wastewater

Line	Slopes	S_{xx}	RSD	t	t 95%
Wastewater	0.0935	40	0.0203	0.979	2.31
Water	0.0421	40	0.01923	1.73	-
Calibration curve	0.08962	68.8	0.0319	-	-

Interferences :

Ions that don't interfere in concentration up to 1000 mg/L are Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , CO_3^{2-} , and SO_4^{2-} . AsO_3^{3-} , AsO_4^{3-} and SO_3^{2-} do not affect results if concentrations are less than 100 mg/L. Effect of VO_3^- was not examined because it is known³⁻⁶ that the amounts of VO_3^- upto five times more than P_2O_5 do not interfere. Examination of silicate interference revealed that silica upto ten times more than P_2O_5 do not interfere because malachite green/silicomolybdic acid complex^{5,6,10} is very difficult to form.

Comparison of results :

Various samples of water and wastewater were analyzed employing the proposed method and the existing colorimetric method¹, in duplicate. Table 2 show the results of these determinations which illustrate that the repeatabilities are similar with water and wastewater samples. The values of this parameter are smaller then the calculated 95% confidence limit. The proposed technique was compared with the

Table 2. Results of paired t -tests in comparison of the methods

Sample	Mean difference	Standard deviation of the difference	No. of samples	t obtained	t 95%
Water	2.81	7.24	24	1.69	2.10
Wastewater	6.28	33.97	66	1.42	2.00

existing¹ method and found to be more sensitive and selective. It offers advantages like reliability and reproducibility in addition to simplicity, instant colour development. Silicate interference was examined and silica upto ten times more than P_2O_5 do not interfere because malachite green/silicomolybdic acid complex^{5,6,10} is very difficult to form.

Conclusion :

The proposed technique is highly sensitive, simple, it can employ a common blank and calibration curve made with standard solution owing to its high recovery and lack of chormophore-matrix interaction. The use of malachite green is specially favored because of its high sensitivity and the absence of interferences by silicates, an aspect that has hindered the use of molybdenum blue¹ method. Amounts of silica upto 10 times more than P_2O_5 do not interfere. The procedure reported is a new approach for the detection of phosphate in water. It is found to give very good results with phosphate levels between 0.001–10 mg P/L. It may however be noted that the reagent (Tween 20) is stable for 48 h.

Experimental

Standard procedures of APHA¹ were followed for collection, sampling, filtration and storage. Samples of water from shallow handpumps (≈ 20 m depth) and tubewells (≈ 60 m depth) were collected around a fertilizer unit and around a drain which carries city's domestic and industrial sewage.

All the reagents used were of analytical grade and solution were prepared in conductivity water (2–10 μS).

Stock reagents : Following reagents were required : (i) ammonium heptamolybdate (Merck) at 1.75% m/v in 2.1N H_2SO_4 stored in a plastic bottle, (ii) malachite green (Ranbaxy) at 0.25% m/v containing Tween 20 (Merck) dissolved previously in water and (iii) the stock phosphate solution was prepared by dissolving 109.75 mg KH_2PO_4 (Merck) oven dried for 1 h at 105°.

Working reagents : Standard phosphate solution : The standard solution (12 mg/L) was made by diluting the stock solution.

Reagent-K : Ammonium heptamolybdate (1.665 g) was

dissolved in 2.1 N H₂SO₄ (500 ml).

Reagent-S : Various solutions all containing 7.5 mg of malachite green/100 ml and Tween 20/100 ml in the ratios of 1 : 2 : 3 : 4 : 5 : 6 mg, respectively. In order to optimize reaction conditions the minimal concentrations of molybdate ion and malachite green necessary for maintaining the absorbance were determined. Weight of the ammonium molybdate and malachite green in the final volume should be 52.5 and 7.5 mg, respectively.

The colour was developed using different "S" solutions and absorption spectra were taken at 600 nm in a 1 cm cuvette against a blank in the same reagent.

Procedure :

An aliquot of sample solution containing a phosphate not more than 10 mg/L was mixed with reagent-K (3 ml) and reagent-S (3 ml). The colour was developed during 30 min and its absorption was measured at 600 nm on a Shimadzu UV-260 spectrophotometer. Similar procedure was applied for water and wastewater samples.

Kinetics of chromophore formation : Solution of 2.5 and 10 mg/L of KH₂PO₄ were prepared and 1 ml of each was pipetted into 10 tubes respectively. Reagents-K and S were added to all and mixed. Different tubes of the two series were read at different times against a blank with the same time of mixing.

Youden's^{9,10} blank determinations :

Samples of water and wastewater of the various described sources were taken into test tubes in triplicate and colour was developed according to the proposed technique, the obtained curve of absorption versus quantity of sample was adjusted by the least square method^{9,10} and the intercept and slope were also determined.

Calibration curve :

Stock solutions ranging from 2–12 mg/L of KH₂PO₄ were prepared and colour was developed employing the proposed technique. A calibration curve was made by

plotting the curve as absorbance versus phosphate (mg/L) content. The phosphate content in water and wastewater samples was determined with the help of this calibration curve.

Recovery determinations :

Various samples of water and wastewater were diluted to half the usual concentrations, 0.5 ml of each sample was pipetted into test tubes and 0.5 ml of standard solutions of 2.5, 5.0, 7.5 and 10.0 mg/L of KH₂PO₄ were added. The colour was developed according to the proposed method and plots of absorbance versus phosphate added were drawn. These were adjusted by the least square method^{9,10} and the intercept and slopes obtained were compared with the calibration curve.

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